

NOVEL HYBRID TITANIA NANOCOMPOSITES AS EFFICIENT AND RECYCLABLE PHOTOCATALYST

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SUMMARY

Four types of novel hybrid titania nanocomposites including titania nanoparticles immobilized on ZnO tetrapods, hollow silica/titania microspheres, polystyrene/silica/titania spheres and titania/silica-coated magnetic spheres have been prepared with well controlled microstructure. They showed higher photocatalytic activity in the degradation of phenol or methylene blue under UV or visible light irradiation with easy to be separated and recyclable use feature.

Keywords: hybrid, titania, photocatalyst, nanocomposite

ABSTRACT

Anatase TiO₂ nanoparticles with size of 6nm were immobilized on the single-crystalline tetrapod-like ZnO template by vapor hydrolysis method. Well-defined nitrogen-doped, hollow SiO₂/TiO₂ hybrid spheres, PS/SiO₂/TiO₂ multilayer hybrid spheres and tianina/silica-coated magnetic spheres were formed by two-step sol-gel methods. The as-prepared hybrid nanocomposites were characterized by SEM, TEM, X-ray diffraction, EDS, thermogravimetric analysis, and N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherm analysis. They showed higher photocatalytic activity in the degradation of phenol or methylene blue under UV or visible light irradiation with recyclable feature. This work provides a novel avenue to the synthesis of hybrid materials with complicated structure, offering a new material platform for catalyst, microelectronic, and other applications.

Experimental Section

Taking the preparation of SiO₂/TiO₂ hybrid hollow microspheres as an example, first, the cationic polystyrene core templates of 262 nm diameter were fabricated by emulsifier-free emulsion polymerization using the cationic initiator. Second, the coating reaction of PS beads could be directly processed at room temperature by a modified stöber procedure, a commonly used sol-gel method to get amorphous silica. Then, TiO₂ nanoparticles aggregated and grew by refluxing at 80°C for 2h with Ti(OBu)₄ as titanium source and PVP as surfactant. Third, the polystyrene cores were removed by calcination in a furnace.

Results and Discussion

The hybrids of ZnO@TiO₂ core/shell heterostructures, SiO₂/TiO₂ hybrid hollow microspheres and tianina/silica-coated magnetic spheres have been prepared (Fig. 1). From Fig. 1a, it can be seen that TiO₂ nanoparticles aggregate on the rod-like ZnO, spherical PS/SiO₂ grow up into the desired morphologies and titania/silica particles coated on Fe₃O₄ particle homogenously. They showed higher photocatalytic activity in the degradation of phenol or methylene blue under UV or visible light irradiation with easy to be separated and recyclable use feature.

Figure 1 TEM images of (a) ZnO@TiO₂ heterostructures, (b) PS/SiO₂/TiO₂ heterostructures, (c) SEM image of SiO₂/TiO₂ hybrid hollow microspheres and (d) tianina/silica-coated magnetic spheres

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